

Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

In 1740 to 1744, Commodore George Anson led a squadron of eight ships on a mission to disrupt or capture the Spanish possessions in the Pacific. The voyage was notable for its horrific losses, with only 188 men of the original 1,854 crew and officers surviving. Most of the deaths were due to scurvy. Out of the eight ships, only one ship completed the voyage. An account of the voyage was published in 1748. This is a summary of scurvy on Anson's voyage by James Lind in his *Treatise on the Scurvy* (1772).

James Lind¹ dedicated his *Treatise of the Scurvy* (1st and 2nd eds.) to Lord Anson:

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=9> First ed. 1753.

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/ii/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30507054/page/n7/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/hkvrjpk9/items?canvas=7> Second ed. 1757.

https://archive.org/details/b30515622_0001/page/n5/mode/2up

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216015&seq=7>

Lord Anson, who was at the time First Lord Commissioner of the Admiralty, was probably responsible for getting Lind appointed in 1758 chief Physician to the new Royal Naval Hospital – Haslar Hospital.²

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397301>

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<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.fi/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

1 Selections of Lind's texts, and links to digitized books, and links to numerous biographies on Lind:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

2 Guthrie D, Meiklejohn AP. James Lind and Some of his Contemporaries. 1953.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10605213>

Stockman R. James Lind and Scurvy. *Edinb Med J.* 1926 Jun;33(6):329-350.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5302666>

"In the 1740s, it [Haslar Hospital] was the largest hospital in the world, and the largest brick-building in Europe."

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Royal_Hospital_Haslar

<https://www.royalhaslar.com/history>

<https://www.jameslindlibrary.org/articles/the-royal-hospital-haslar-from-lind-to-the-21st-century>

Anson's voyage round the world by Walter

A voyage round the world, in the years 1740, 41, 42, 43, 44, by George Anson, Esq.; now Lord Anson, commander in chief of a squadron of his Majesty's ships, sent upon an expedition to the South seas. Compiled from his papers and materials, by Richard Walter,³ M.A. &c.

Walter's book has been extensively digitized with over 20 versions available:

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001876458>

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<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/100264669>

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/100278130>

<https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld00walt/page/n5/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld00walt_0/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld00walt_1/page/n3/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld00walt_2/page/n5/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld00waltuoft/page/n9/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/gri_33125011256381/page/n3/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.42984/page/n7/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/voyageroundworld0000walt/page/n7/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/cihm_17410/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_18288/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_27757/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_27900/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_32030/page/n5/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_32032/page/n5/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/cu31924023252152/page/n5/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/voyageautourdum00waltgoog/page/n2/mode/2up> (French)

https://archive.org/details/cihm_17436/page/n7/mode/2up (French)

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_GGNyAAAaAAJ/page/n5/mode/2up (German)

<https://archive.org/details/desherrnadmiraals00walt/page/n5/mode/2up> (German)

<https://archive.org/details/reizerondsomdewe00walt/page/n5/mode/2up> (Dutch)

Book reviews:

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1784959>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/40559079>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/513976>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/566242>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1784959>

3 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richard_Walter_\(chaplain\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richard_Walter_(chaplain))

Other texts related to Anson and Anson's voyage

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Anson,_1st_Baron_Anson
<https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1715-1754/member/anson-george-1697-1762>
<https://www.britannica.com/biography/George-Anson-Baron-Anson>
<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-13991>
<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-13990>
<https://the-past.com/feature/master-and-commander/>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Anson%27s_voyage_around_the_world
<https://www.usni.org/magazines/naval-history-magazine/2023/august/ansons-voyage>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc9662994>

The life of George, Lord Anson, by Sir John Barrow⁴ (1839)

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/005794396>
<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/100263876>
<https://archive.org/details/lifeofgeorgelord00barr/page/n11/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/lifegeorgelorda02barrgoog/page/n3/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/lifegeorgelorda00barrgoog/page/n6/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/lifegeorgelorda01barrgoog/page/n10/mode/2up>

The life of Admiral Lord Anson, the father of the British navy, 1697-1762, by Walter Vernon Anson (1912)

<https://archive.org/details/lifeofadmirallor00anso/page/n1/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/lifeofadmirallor00ansoof/page/n9/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/cu31924027914807/page/n9/mode/2up>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/44990111>

The prize of all the oceans: Commodore Anson's daring voyage and triumphant capture of the Spanish treasure galleon, by Glyn Williams⁵ (2001)

https://archive.org/details/prizeofalloeans0000will_o5i8
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<https://doi.org/10.25290/prinunivlibrchro.64.2.0289>
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<https://doi.org/10.2307/4053467>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/40108612>
<https://www.publishersweekly.com/9780670891979>

Documents Relating to Anson's Voyage Round the World, 1740-1744, by Glyndwr Williams (1967)

<https://www.navyrecords.org.uk/documents-relating-to-ansons-voyage-round-the-world-1740-1744/>
<https://read.dukeupress.edu/hahr/article/48/4/699/157913/Documents-Relating-to-Anson-s-Voyage-Round-the>
<https://doi.org/10.1086/ahr/73.5.1525>
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2510937>
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1851436>
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1796436>

4 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sir_John_Barrow,_1st_Baronet

5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Glyndwr_Williams

Commodore Anson's voyage into the South seas and around the world, by Boyle Somerville⁶ (1934)

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001270905>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1786821>

Anson: Royal Naval Commander and Statesman, 1697-1762, by Anthony Bruce (2023)

<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/library/rmg1-157746>

<https://www.naval-review.com/book-reviews/anson-royal-navy-commander-and-statesman-1697-1762/>

<https://tnm.journals.yorku.ca/index.php/default/article/view/1177/1132>

Anson's Navy: Building a Fleet for Empire 1744-1763, by Brian Lavery (2022)

<https://www.usni.org/press/books/ansons-navy>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/48732049>

Log of the Centurion: Based on the Original Papers of Captain Philip Saumarez on Board HMS Centurion, Lord Anson's Flagship during His Circumnavigation, 1740-44, by Leo Heaps (1973)

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1796542>

Anson's Voyage, by L. A. Wilcox (1969)

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1796343>

Admiral Lord Anson, by S. W. C. Pack (1960)

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1921193>

Art and War in the Pacific World: Making, Breaking, and Taking from Anson's Voyage to the Philippine-American War, by J. M. Mancini (2018)

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26739798>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26861099>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/48543037>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/48771568>

An affecting narrative of the unfortunate voyage and catastrophe of his Majesty's ship Wager,⁷ one of Commodore Anson's squadron in the South Sea expedition, by Unknown (1751)

<https://archive.org/details/affectingnarrati00unkn/page/n5/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_an-affecting-narrative-o_1751

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boyle_Somerville

⁷ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Wager_\(1739\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Wager_(1739))

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wager_Mutiny

The text below is from James Lind's *Treatise on the Scurvy* (1772; 3rd ed) p. 440-448.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/440/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/440/mode/2up>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=464>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=462>

1748.

A voyage round the world, in the years 1740, 41, 42, 43, 44, by George Anson, Esq; late Lord Anson, commander in chief of a squadron of his Majesty's ships, sent upon an expedition to the south seas. Compiled from his papers and materials, by Richard Walter, M. A. &c.

Soon after our passing straits *Le Maire*,⁸ p.440
the **scurvy** began to make its appearance amongst us: and our long continuance at sea, the fatigue we underwent, and the various disappointments we met with, had occasioned its spreading to such a degree, that, at the latter end of *April*, there were but few on board who were not in some degree afflicted with it; and in that month no less than forty-three died of it on board the *Centurion*.⁹ But though we thought, that the distemper had then risen to an extraordinary height; and were willing to hope, that as we advanced to the northward, its malignity would abate: yet we found, on the contrary, that, in the month of *May*, we lost near double that number. And as we did not get to land till the middle of *June*, the mortality went on increasing; so that, after the loss of above 200 men, we could not at last muster more than six fore-

8 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Le_Maire_Strait
<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-202483>

9 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Centurion_\(1732\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Centurion_(1732))
<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-66403>
<https://warhistory.org/@msw/article/60-gun-centurion-of-1732>

most men in a watch, capable of duty.

This disease, so frequently attending all long voyages, and so particularly destructive to us, is surely the most singular and unaccountable of any that affects the human body.

p.441

Its symptoms are unconstant and innumerable, and its progress and effects extremely irregular: for scarcely any two persons have the same complaints; and where there hath been found some conformity in the symptoms, the order of their appearance has been totally different. However, though it frequently puts on the form of many other diseases, and is therefore not to be described by any exclusive and infallible criterions; yet there are some symptoms which are more general than the rest, and occurring the oftenest, deserve a more particular enumeration. These common appearances are, large discoloured spots dispersed over the whole surface of the body; swelled legs; putrid gums; and above all, an extraordinary lassitude of the whole body, especially after any exercise, however inconsiderable and this lassitude at last degenerates into a proneness to swoon, on the least exertion of strength, or even on the least motion. This disease is likewise usually attended with a strange dejection of spirits; and with shiverings, tremblings, and a disposition to be seized with the most dreadful terrors on the slightest accident. Indeed it was most remarkable, in all our reiterated experience of this malady, that whatever discouraged our people, or at any time damped their hopes, never failed to add new vigour to the distemper: for it usually killed those who were in the last stages of it, and confined those to their hammocks who were before capable of some kind of duty. So that it seemed, as if alacrity of mind, and sanguine thoughts, were no contemptible preservatives from its fatal malignity.

p.442

But it is not easy to complete the long roll

of the various concomitants of this disease. For it often produced putrid fevers, pleurisies, the jaundice, and violent rheumatic pains. And sometimes it occasioned an obstinate costiveness; which was generally attended with a difficulty of breathing; and this was esteemed the most deadly of all the scorbutic symptoms. At other times the whole body, but more especially the legs, were subject to ulcers of the worst kind, attended with rotten bones, and such a luxuriance of fungous flesh as yielded to no remedy. But a most extraordinary circumstance, and what would be scarcely credible upon any single evidence, is, that the scars of wounds which had been for many years healed, were forced open again by this virulent distemper. Of this there was a remarkable instance in one of the invalids on board the *Centurion*, who had been wounded above fifty years before at the battle of the *Boyne*:¹⁰ for though he was cured soon after, and had continued well for a great number of years past; yet, on his being attacked by the scurvy, his wounds, in the progress of his disease, broke out afresh, and appeared as if they never had been healed. Nay, what is still more astonishing, the *callus* of a broken bone, which had been compleatly formed for a long time, was found to be hereby dissolved; and the fracture seemed as if it had never been consolidated. Indeed, the effects of this disease were in almost every instance wonderful. For many of our people, though confined to their hammocks, appeared to have no inconsiderable share of health; for they eat and drank heartily, were chearful, and talked with much seeming vigour, and with a loud strong tone of voice; and yet on their being the least moved, though it was

p.443

10 “the Battle of the Boyne was the largest engagement ever to take place on Irish soil.”
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_the_Boyne
<https://www.nam.ac.uk/explore/battle-boyne>
<https://www.britannica.com/event/Battle-of-the-Boyne>

only from one part of the ship to the other, and that in their hammocks, they have immediately expired. And others, who have confided in their seeming strength, and have resolved to get out of their hammocks, have died before they could well reach the deck. And it was no uncommon thing for those who could do some kind of duty, and walk the deck, to drop down dead in an instant, on any endeavours to act with their utmost vigour; many of our people having perished in this manner, during the course of this voyage.

Upon arriving at the island of *Juan Fernandes*,¹¹ 167 sick persons were put on shore, besides at least a dozen who died in the boats, on their being exposed to the fresh air. The extreme weakness of the sick may be collected from the numbers who died after they got on shore: for it had generally been found, that the land, and the refreshments it produces, very soon recover most stages of the sea-scurvy; yet it was near twenty days after their landing, before the mortality was tolerably ceased: and for the first ten or twelve days, they buried rarely less than six each day; and many of those who survived, recovered by very slow and insensible degrees. Indeed those who were well enough, at their first getting on shore, to creep out of their tents, and crawl about, were soon relieved, and recovered their health and strength in a very short time; but in the rest, the disease seemed to have acquired a degree of inveteracy altogether without example.

It was very remarkable what happened to the *Gloucester*,¹² which, like the other ships in that squadron, had suffered the most unparalleled hardships, and buried three fourths of her crew in this disease; that,

p.444

11 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Juan_Fern%C3%A1ndez_Islands
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robinson_Crusoe_Island
<https://www.britannica.com/place/Juan-Fernandez-Islands>

12 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Gloucester_\(1711\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HMS_Gloucester_(1711))

upon landing the remainder of her sick, less than eighty in number, very few of them died. Whether it was (as the ingenious author observes) that the farthest advanced in the distemper were already dead, or the greens and fresh provisions sent on board them when plying off that island, had prepared those who remained for a speedy recovery; their sick, however, in general, got much sooner well than the *Centurion's* crew.

p.445

The havock which this dreadful calamity made in those ships, was truly surprising. The *Centurion*, from her leaving *England*, when at this island, had buried 292 men, and had but 214 remaining of her complement. The *Gloucester*, out of a smaller complement, buried the same number, and had only 82 alive. This dreadful mortality had fallen severer on the invalids and marines than on the sailors: for on board the *Centurion*, out of fifty invalids, and seventy-nine marines, there remained only four invalids, including officers, and eleven marines; and on board the *Gloucester*, every invalid died, and only two marines escaped out of forty-eight.

In less, however, than seven weeks after leaving the coast of *Mexico*, having continued in perfect health for a considerable time before, this fatal disease broke out again amongst them. Upon which occasion, the ingenious author makes the following remarks.

Some amongst us were willing to believe, that in this warm climate the violence of the disease, and its fatality, might be in some degree mitigated. But the ravage of the distemper at that time convinced them of the falsity of this speculation; as it likewise exploded other opinions about the cause and nature of this disease. For it has been generally presumed, that plenty of water, and of fresh provisions, are effectual preventives of this malady. But it happened

p.446

in the present case, we had a considerable stock of fresh provisions on board, being the hogs and fowls taken at *Paita*.¹³ We besides, almost daily, caught great abundance of bonito's,¹⁴ dolphins and albacores:¹⁵ and the unsettled season having proved extremely rainy, supplied us with plenty of water; so that each man had five pints a-day during the passage. But notwithstanding this plenty of water, and fresh provisions distributed among the sick, the whole crew often fed upon fish; yet neither were the sick hereby relieved, nor the progress and advancement of the disease retarded. It has likewise been believed by many, that keeping the ship clean and airy betwixt decks, might prevent, or at least mitigate the scurvy: yet we observed, during the latter part of our run, that, though we kept all our ports open, and took uncommon pains in sweetening and cleansing the ship; yet neither the progress, nor the virulence of the disease were thereby sensibly abated. The surgeon at this time having declared, that all his measures were totally ineffectual for the relief of his patients, it was resolved to try the effects of *Ward's* drop and pill;¹⁶ and one, or both of them, at different times, were given to persons in every stage of the distemper. Out of the numbers who took them, one, soon after swallowing the pill, was seized with a violent bleeding at the nose. He was before given over by the surgeon, and lay almost at the point of death; but he immediately found himself much better, and continued to recover, though slowly, till we arrived

p.447

13 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paita>
<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-11850>
<https://catalogue.nla.gov.au/catalog/505124>

14 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bonito>

15 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Albacore>

16 Ward "invented a medicine called 'Joshua Ward's drop', also known as the 'Pill and Drop'. It was supposed to cure people of any illness they had, gaining acclaim and notoriety for Ward" https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Joshua_Ward
<https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1715-1754/member/ward-joshua-1685-1761>
<https://sloaneletters.com/people/joshua-ward/>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xgbzazkj/items?canvas=5>

on shore near a fortnight after. A few others were relieved for some days.¹⁷ But the disease returned again with as much virulence as ever; though neither did these, nor the rest who received no benefit, appear to be reduced to a worse condition than they would have been if they had taken nothing. The most remarkable property of these medicines in almost every one that took them, was, that they operated in proportion to the vigour of the patient. So that those who were within two or three days of dying, were scarcely affected; and as the patient was differently advanced in the disease, the operation was either a gentle perspiration, an easy vomit, or a moderate purge. But if they were taken by one in full strength, they then produced all the before-mentioned effects with considerable violence; which sometimes continued for six or eight hours together with little intermission. Upon their arrival at *Tinian*,¹⁸ they soon began to feel the salutary influence of the land: for though they had buried in two days before twenty-one men, yet they did not lose above ten more from the day after they were landed; and reaped so much benefit from the fruits of the island, particularly those of the acid kind, that in a week's time there were but, few of them who were not so far recovered as to be able to move about without help.

p.448

17 This is explained by the placebo effect.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Placebo#Effects>
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.59.113006.095941>

18 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tinian,_Northern_Mariana_Islands
<https://www.guammuseumfoundation.org/in-1742-anson-and-what-was-left-of-his-expedition-arrived-in-tinian/>
<https://www.britannica.com/place/Tinian>
<https://www.nps.gov/articles/000/tinian-island-during-the-manhattan-project.htm>